

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL METHODS OF STUDYING CHILDREN WITH HEARING DEFECTS

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Abstract. It provides information about psychological and pedagogical methods of studying children with hearing impairment. Sign pedagogy uses various research methods to develop and study the process of education for children with hearing impairment.

Keywords: hearing, boarding school, observation, deaf children, interview method, chart, picture, exhibition.

Educational-educational boarding schools for hearing-impaired children systematic goal-directed learning of the process-pedagogical observation is counted. The task of observation is to gather evidence, organize and analyze it. The observer observes the child's activities and these observations allow the collection of negative and positive evidence. The method of studying the activities of deaf children is important in determining the level of their knowledge and skills. The child's drawing, paper and plasticine products are analyzed. Not only the final result is analyzed, but also the execution process, the mistakes made and the lessons learned in solving the difficulties are analyzed.

Refer to psychological and pedagogical examination in case of impaired hearing function to do, inspection work should be carried out using specific game materials

(spreading and assembling matryoshkas, placing sticks based on the given pattern

output, the skill of counting pyramid circles, about the number of items formation of concepts. Tables and pictures are widely used during psychological and pedagogical examination.

Tasks given to deaf children during the use of tables and pictures they do it with the help of gestures and dactyl speech. Another common method is the survey method. When conducting the survey method, it is important to clarify the questions that correspond to the research task. The survey method allows to determine the interests, worldviews, orientations of the participants, to analyze the studied phenomena in depth.

Interviews with deaf and hard-of-hearing children provide necessary information for research is used in obtaining. The effect of the conversation is to create a natural psychological atmosphere, it depends on the researcher's ability to communicate with the subject, and the pedagogue should be prepared in advance for targeted questions. The content of the conversation is recorded in the report. Studying pedagogical documents (lesson notes, extracurricular work notes, educational process plans) helps to gain an understanding of the educational process implemented in the school and the results achieved by the team of pedagogues. Gives the formation of speech in deaf children saved all the remaining analyzers is based on application in special educational conditions. Visual perception, tactile-vibrational sense and kinesthetic feeling can be involved only with the help of a deaf teacher. The social environment of a deaf child, the nature of activities in the family affects not only the child's overall development, but also the formation of communication tools.

Selection and sequencing of one or another method used depends on the examiner's age and individual characteristics. During the inspection it is important to add tasks, support options, educational elements of a similar nature, through which the child's ability to transfer the indicated activity paths to other activities is demonstrated. Tasks should be verbal and non-verbal.

When examining a child, it is important to take into account the following indicators:

1. Child's emotional reaction to research (examination). Excitement is a natural reaction to new situations and unfamiliar people. It should be more cheerful than usual.

2. Understanding the purpose and instructions of the assignment. To the end of the instruction.

Are they listening, trying to understand first, and then getting to work?

What type of instruction is understandable to the child: verbal or verbal and visual

with a demonstration?

3. Nature of activity during performance. Stagnation of task and interest and availability, goal-orientedness of the child's activity, ability to finish the work. It is necessary to pay attention to correct and rational actions, concentration of attention in the work process. The general working ability of the child is taken into account. One

of the key indicators is access to help. The more this ability is evident, the more teachable the child is.

4. Reacting to the work result. Critical assessment of one's own work, an adequate emotional reaction (joy at success, sadness at failure), child shows that he understands the situation correctly.

Interview method. Conversational communication has its own characteristics, it cannot be replaced by filling out any questionnaire or questionnaire.

It is not recommended to conduct the interview in the form of a dry question and answer, it is a game in the process, even when the child sees an interesting object or picture can be transferred. Conversation is important in the later stages of research becomes important, it awakens a sense of trust in the examiner and

helps in ensuring the correct attitude towards the performance of tasks. Conversation. What to focus on in this case, giving the opportunity to draw up an inspection plan helps to determine what is needed.

A more in-depth examination of what aspects of speaking in conversation can be determined. Therefore, the conversation is a part of the child's life clarifies that aspects should be specially studied and given relative importance. The transition from conversation to checking other types of activities should be planned, not difficult for the child, and purposeful.

In conclusion, good results can be achieved if the above methods are used correctly and wisely.

REFERENCES

1. D.A.Nurkeldiyeva, M.U.Hamidova "Diagnostics of children with developmental disabilities" Tashkent - 2016;
2. Rakhmanova V.S. "Correctional pedagogy and speech therapy". Tashkent "Economy - Finance" 2007;
3. M.Y. Ayupova "Logopedia". Tashkent Publishing House of the National Society of Philosophers of Uzbekistan 2007;